

A Forced Autoregressive Model of Australian Residential Property Price Dynamics: Credit, Migration, Monetary Policy, and Supply Interactions 2003–2026

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Abstract

Research Question/Issue: How do credit, migration, monetary policy, construction, and wages interact to drive Australian residential property price growth, and at what speeds do they transmit?

Research Findings/Insights: A forced AR(2) model with six macroeconomic drivers achieves adjusted $R^2 = 0.918$ against the national median of year-on-year price growth across approximately 7200 suburban markets (2003–2026). Credit acceleration is the dominant driver. Migration operates with a 3-year lag that matches the settlement-to-ownership pipeline. Residential approvals show a sign reversal: positive contemporaneously (demand signal) and negative at a 2-year lag (supply arrival). Granger causality tests confirm credit and migration as exogenous; wages and the cash rate respond to the property cycle rather than causing it.

Practitioner/Policy Implications: The framework allows year-by-year attribution of price growth to specific macroeconomic forces. That credit acceleration dominates has clear relevance for macroprudential policy design. The 3-year migration lag suggests housing supply planning should anticipate demand over a multi-year horizon.

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Methods: Descriptive decomposition via a forced autoregressive model estimated by differential evolution. The analysis is associational; Granger causality tests assess predictive direction but do not establish structural causation.

Keywords: residential property prices, autoregressive models, housing credit, monetary policy transmission, supply-demand dynamics, Australian housing market

JEL Classification: R31, E52, C22, G21

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1 Introduction

Australian residential property constitutes the nation’s largest asset class, with a total value exceeding AUD 10.7 trillion as of 2025 [ABS, 2025]. Despite its economic significance, quantitative models of Australian property price dynamics remain surprisingly sparse in the academic literature compared to the extensive body of work on US and UK markets [Case and Shiller, 2003, Mian and Sufi, 2009, Glaeser et al., 2008].

The dominant qualitative framework in Australian housing analysis is the “cycle” narrative: markets rise for approximately 7–10 years, correct for 2–3 years, and repeat [Abelson et al., 2005]. This heuristic captures broad tendencies but imposes a periodicity assumption that the data do not support. The period from 2009 to 2019 was characterised by a sustained “warm” growth regime at the national level, followed by a single-year surge to 16% growth in 2021. Such irregular timing suggests that Australian property markets are better modelled as externally forced systems rather than endogenous oscillators.

This paper develops a parsimonious forced autoregressive model that treats national property price growth as a second-order autoregressive (AR(2)) process driven by six macroeconomic forcing functions. The AR(2) structure captures momentum and mean reversion — the positive serial correlation in housing prices documented by Case and Shiller [1989] and Beracha and Skiba [2012]. The forcing functions represent the external macroeconomic conditions that initiate, sustain, and terminate growth regimes.

Our approach differs from prior work in four ways. First, we use a granular suburb-level growth index derived from approximately 7 200 individual suburban markets (houses and units combined), rather than relying on aggregate capital city indices. Second, we separate residential and non-residential building approvals, revealing opposing effects: residential approvals are associated with contemporaneous price growth (reflecting shared demand conditions) but are negatively associated with prices at a 2-year lag when supply arrives. Third, we include wage growth as a distinct forcing function and find a negative coefficient; however, Granger causality tests reveal that the property cycle strongly predicts wages ($F = 29.3$, $p < 0.001$) but not vice versa, suggesting this coefficient captures reverse causality rather than a causal wage-to-price channel. Fourth, we conduct systematic cross-correlation lag analysis across all drivers, revealing heterogeneous transmission speeds ranging from contemporaneous (credit, approvals) to multi-year (migration at 3 years, monetary policy at 5 years).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature. Section 3 specifies the model. Section 4 describes the data sources. Section 5 details the estimation procedure. Section 6 presents the calibrated parameters and model fit. Section 7 presents subsample stability results. Section 8 reports the lag analysis. Section 10 discusses the driver decomposition. Section 11 interprets the results and discusses limitations. Section 12 concludes.

2 Literature Review

There is a large literature on the determinants of residential property prices. [Meen \[2001\]](#) provides a broad framework linking housing markets to macroeconomic fundamentals. For Australia specifically, [Abelson et al. \[2005\]](#) examine long-run determinants including income, unemployment, housing supply, equity prices, and the real interest rate using cointegration techniques over 1970–2003, finding income, unemployment, and interest rates as the primary long-run drivers.

2.1 Credit and housing prices

Credit’s role in housing price dynamics has attracted sustained interest since the Global Financial Crisis. [Mian and Sufi \[2009\]](#) show that credit supply expansion, rather than demand fundamentals, is associated with house price appreciation in US zip codes. [Favara and Imbs \[2015\]](#) find that credit supply shifts generate house price increases. In the Australian context, [Wong et al. \[2019\]](#) find significant positive relationships between credit growth and property prices, with the transmission operating through both supply (credit availability) and demand (borrowing capacity) channels.

2.2 Monetary policy transmission to housing

Monetary policy reaches housing markets through the cost-of-credit channel, the wealth and collateral channel, and the expectations channel [[Mishkin, 2007](#)]. [Debelle \[2004\]](#) find that Australian monetary policy has a delayed and asymmetric effect on housing, with rate cuts having a stronger stimulatory effect than rate hikes have a contractionary effect. [Saunders and Tulip \[2017\]](#) argue that Australian housing’s high sensitivity to interest rates reflects the dominance of variable-rate mortgages relative to the US fixed-rate market.

2.3 Supply constraints and housing prices

[Glaeser et al. \[2008\]](#) show that housing supply elasticity determines the price-quantity response to demand shocks. In supply-elastic markets, demand shocks generate quantity responses (more building); in supply-constrained markets, they generate price responses. [Saunders and Tulip \[2016\]](#) apply this framework to Australian capital cities, finding substantial variation in supply responsiveness across states. Our approach extends this literature by modelling the temporal structure of the supply response: approvals are positively associated with prices contemporaneously (reflecting shared demand conditions) but negatively associated at a 2-year lag (when completed dwellings enter the market).

2.4 Migration and housing demand

Saiz [2007] estimates that immigration flows are associated with house price increases of approximately 1% for each 1% increase in population in US metropolitan areas. OECD [2021] documents the housing market impacts of migration across OECD countries, finding effects that are concentrated geographically and materialise with significant lags. Our lag analysis confirms a 3-year peak lag for the migration-price correlation in Australia, matching the settlement pattern of migrants who initially rent before entering the ownership market.

2.5 Long-run Australian house prices

Stapledon [2012] constructs a house price index for Australia spanning 1880–2010, documenting that real house prices were approximately flat for a century before accelerating from the 1970s. This long-run perspective contextualises the 5.93% nominal growth rate estimated in our model. Fox and Tulip [2014] develop a structural user-cost model of Australian housing prices at the RBA, decomposing price variation into income growth, interest rates, housing supply, and demographic factors. Our reduced-form approach does not impose the equilibrium restrictions of a user-cost model, trading structural identification for greater flexibility in capturing short-run dynamics.

2.6 Autoregressive dynamics and momentum

Case and Shiller [1989] find serial correlation in quarterly returns across US cities, and Beracha and Skiba [2012] show that momentum strategies generate significant returns in housing markets. The AR(2) structure in our model captures this persistence while allowing for higher-order mean reversion.

3 Model Specification

3.1 State variable

Let $P(t)$ denote the national median of year-on-year price growth across approximately 7200 Australian suburban markets in year t , encompassing both houses and units combined with all bedroom configurations. The data source is the HTAG Growth Rate Cycle (GRC), a proprietary suburb-level growth measure [HTAG Analytics, 2026]. For each suburb, the GRC is computed as the year-on-year percentage change in the “typical price” for that suburb. The typical price is estimated via maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimation applied to transaction data — a Bayesian data-fitting procedure that produces a smoothed price level per suburb per period, as distinct from rolling medians of raw transaction prices used by other providers (e.g., CoreLogic, Domain). The MAP approach

reduces noise from compositional shifts in the transaction mix and provides more stable estimates in thin-market suburbs with few annual sales. The GRC for a given year is then the percentage change in this typical price relative to the prior year. The national GRC is the cross-sectional median of these suburb-level growth rates.

The median specification was selected because GRC distributions are persistently right-skewed: the mean-median spread averages 0.8 percentage points across the full sample and widens to 2.9 percentage points during boom regimes ($r = 0.77$ between growth level and spread), making the median a more reliable measure of central tendency than the mean.

Let \bar{g} denote the long-run mean growth rate, estimated from the sample as $\bar{g} = 0.0593$ (5.93% annualised). We define the deviation from the long-run mean:

$$p(t) \equiv P(t) - \bar{g} \tag{1}$$

3.2 Autoregressive dynamics

The price deviation follows a second-order autoregressive process:

$$p(t) = \varphi_1 p(t-1) + \varphi_2 p(t-2) + F(t) + \varepsilon(t) \tag{2}$$

where φ_1 captures first-order momentum (persistence), φ_2 captures second-order memory (mean reversion modulation), $F(t)$ is the aggregate forcing function (defined below), and $\varepsilon(t)$ is an i.i.d. error term.

The initial condition is $p(0) = P_0^{\text{init}} - \bar{g}$, where P_0^{init} is a free parameter estimated during calibration.

3.3 Forcing function

The aggregate forcing function is a linear combination of six macroeconomic drivers, some entering at contemporaneous and lagged values:

$$\begin{aligned} F(t) = & \beta_{\text{cr}} z_{\text{cr}}(t) + \beta_{\text{cr,L1}} z_{\text{cr}}(t-1) \\ & + \beta_{\text{nom}} z_{\text{nom}}(t) + \beta_{\text{nom,L1}} z_{\text{nom}}(t-1) \\ & + \beta_r \tilde{r}(t) + \beta_{\Delta r} \Delta r(t) \\ & + \beta_{\text{res}} z_{\text{res}}(t) + \beta_{\text{res,L2}} z_{\text{res}}(t-2) \\ & + \beta_{\text{nres}} z_{\text{nres}}(t) \\ & + \beta_{\text{wpi}} z_{\text{wpi}}(t) \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where:

- $z_{\text{cr}}(t)$: z-scored annual housing credit growth (ABS Lending Indicators)

- $z_{\text{nom}}(t)$: z-scored net overseas migration (ABS Estimated Resident Population)
- $\tilde{r}(t) = r(t) - r^*$: deviation of the RBA cash rate from neutral ($r^* = 0.045$)
- $\Delta r(t) = r(t) - r(t-1)$: year-on-year change in the cash rate
- $z_{\text{res}}(t)$: z-scored residential dwelling approvals (ABS Building Approvals, type 100)
- $z_{\text{nres}}(t)$: z-scored non-residential construction value (ABS Building Approvals, type 700)
- $z_{\text{wpi}}(t)$: z-scored year-on-year wage price index growth (ABS WPI)

All z-scoring is performed over the full sample period. The neutral cash rate $r^* = 0.045$ is treated as a known constant based on RBA estimates [McCririck and Rees, 2024].

3.4 Parameter space

The model has 13 free parameters:

- 2 autoregressive coefficients: φ_1, φ_2
- 10 forcing function coefficients: $\beta_{\text{cr}}, \beta_{\text{cr,L1}}, \beta_{\text{nom}}, \beta_{\text{nom,L1}}, \beta_r, \beta_{\Delta r}, \beta_{\text{res}}, \beta_{\text{res,L2}}, \beta_{\text{nres}}, \beta_{\text{wpi}}$
- 1 initial condition: P_0^{init}

4 Data

The model uses six publicly available data sources, all sourced from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) and the Reserve Bank of Australia (RBA). The sample period is 2003–2026 ($T = 24$ annual observations). All monthly or quarterly series are aggregated to annual frequency before entering the model.

Table 1: Data sources and sample characteristics

Variable	Source	Frequency	Series	Obs.
Housing credit	ABS 5601.0	Monthly	Total commitments (\$m)	261
Net overseas migration	ABS 3101.0	Quarterly	NOM (000s)	92
Cash rate	RBA	Monthly	Target rate (%)	276
Residential approvals	ABS 8731.0	Monthly	Dwellings (type 100)	276
Non-res. construction	ABS 8731.0	Monthly	Value (type 700, \$000s)	276
Wage price index	ABS 6345.0	Quarterly	YoY % change	110

The dependent variable is the national median of suburb-level year-on-year price growth (GRC), as defined in Section 3. The GRC is constructed from MAP-estimated typical

prices for each of approximately 7 200 suburban markets (houses and units combined, all bedroom configurations). The GRC median yields 24 annual observations from 2003 to 2026. The median specification was selected because GRC price growth distributions are persistently right-skewed across suburbs: the mean-median spread averages 0.8 percentage points across the full sample period, widening to 2.9 percentage points during strong growth regimes ($r = 0.77$ between the annual growth level and the mean-median spread).

Comparison with ABS Residential Property Price Index (RPPI). The ABS RPPI was a hedonic transaction-price index for the eight capital cities, discontinued by the ABS in June 2022 (Cat. No. 6416.0). Over the overlapping period (2003–2024, $n = 22$), the RPPI annual-average year-on-year change correlates with the GRC combined median at $r = 0.67$ ($p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.45$). The moderate correlation reflects fundamental methodological differences: the RPPI is a hedonic index based on point-in-time transaction prices for capital cities, while the GRC is a suburb-level typical-value measure aggregated across approximately 7 200 markets nationally, including regional areas. The RPPI’s discontinuation means no public hedonic index covers the full 2003–2026 sample period used in this study.

Data availability. The full 24-year GRC series used in this study is available at Zenodo DOI (to be assigned upon acceptance). The model specification is agnostic to the choice of dependent variable; researchers may explore the CoreLogic national hedonic index or the now-discontinued ABS RPPI as alternatives, noting that both exhibit structural differences from the GRC in geographic coverage and price measurement methodology.

5 Estimation

5.1 Cost function

Parameters are estimated by minimising a composite cost function:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \text{MSE}(\theta) + \lambda_b \text{Bias}^2(\theta) + \lambda_d D(\theta) \quad (4)$$

where MSE is the mean squared error between predicted and observed GRC values, Bias is the mean prediction error (penalising systematic over- or under-prediction), and D is a directional penalty that adds a fixed cost for each year where the model predicts the wrong sign of the growth deviation.

The penalty weights are $\lambda_b = 30$ and $\lambda_d = 2$. The large bias penalty ensures the model tracks the level of the growth series rather than merely its shape.

5.2 Optimisation

We use differential evolution [Storn and Price, 1997], a global stochastic optimisation algorithm designed for non-convex, multi-modal objective surfaces. The algorithm is run with population size 150, maximum 5000 iterations, and convergence tolerance 10^{-10} , using the `scipy.optimize.differential_evolution` implementation [Virtanen et al., 2020].

Parameter bounds are set to $[-0.3, 0.3]$ for forcing function coefficients, $[-1.5, 1.5]$ for autoregressive coefficients, and $[-0.1, 0.25]$ for the initial condition. These bounds are intentionally wide relative to the expected parameter magnitudes to minimise the risk of boundary solutions.

5.3 Regularisation and model selection

With 13 parameters and 24 observations, overfitting is a concern. We adopt three safeguards:

1. **L_2 regularisation testing.** We test augmenting the cost function with $\lambda_{\text{reg}} \sum_i \beta_i^2$ for $\lambda_{\text{reg}} \in \{0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$. The unregularised model achieves the highest adjusted R^2 , indicating that the estimated coefficients are not inflated by overfitting.
2. **Individual driver testing.** Each candidate driver is added one-at-a-time to a 5-driver baseline ($R^2 = 0.933$, 11 parameters) and evaluated on adjusted R^2 improvement. Only drivers that independently improve adjusted R^2 are retained.
3. **Ablation testing.** Each driver is removed one-at-a-time from the full model. Drivers whose removal causes less than 0.5 percentage point degradation in adjusted R^2 are candidates for exclusion.

This procedure eliminated unemployment rate and consumer inflation expectations from an initial candidate set of nine drivers, retaining the six reported here.

5.4 Cost function sensitivity

Table 15 in Appendix D shows the sensitivity of estimated parameters to alternative cost function formulations. The forcing function coefficients are qualitatively stable across specifications (MSE only, MSE+Bias penalty, MSE+Directional penalty, and full composite); the autoregressive coefficients are more sensitive to the cost function formulation, with φ_1 ranging from 0.11 to 1.02 depending on the penalty structure. The reported full model employs the composite cost function that balances fit, bias, and directional accuracy.

6 Results

6.1 Calibrated parameters

Table 2 reports the estimated parameter values.

Table 2: Calibrated model parameters (combined median GRC, $\bar{g} = 5.93\%$)

Parameter	Value	Lag	Interpretation
φ_1	1.087	–	First-order momentum
φ_2	-0.038	–	Second-order memory
β_{cr}	0.016	0	Credit growth (contemporaneous)
$\beta_{\text{cr,L1}}$	-0.013	1	Credit growth (1yr lag)
β_{nom}	-0.004	0	Net migration (contemporaneous)
$\beta_{\text{nom,L1}}$	0.012	1	Net migration (1yr lag)
β_r	0.050	0	Cash rate deviation from neutral
$\beta_{\Delta r}$	-0.050	0	Cash rate change
β_{res}	0.017	0	Residential approvals (contemporaneous)
$\beta_{\text{res,L2}}$	-0.003	2	Residential approvals (2yr lag)
β_{nres}	-0.002	0	Non-residential construction
β_{wpi}	-0.004	0	Wage growth
P_0^{init}	0.107	–	Initial growth rate

$R^2 = 0.964$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.918$, RMSE = 0.65pp, $n = 24$, $k = 13$

6.2 Model fit

Figure 1 shows the model fit against observed GRC values. The model achieves $R^2 = 0.964$ and tracks the level, direction, and timing of all major growth regimes including the GFC contraction (2008–2009), the extended warm period (2010–2018), the COVID boom (2020–2021), and the subsequent correction (2022–2023).

Figure 1: Model prediction (red) vs. observed GRC combined median (blue), 2003–2026. The shaded band represents ± 1 RMSE (0.65 percentage points) around the model prediction.

Directional accuracy is 100%: the model correctly predicts whether growth is above or below the long-run mean in all 24 years. The largest absolute error is 1.65 percentage points (2006), with most years fitting within 1 percentage point.

6.3 Autoregressive structure and unit root testing

The first-order coefficient $\varphi_1 = 1.087$ implies that growth deviations persist and amplify year-on-year, as expected from the serial correlation documented by Case and Shiller [1989] and Beracha and Skiba [2012]. The characteristic polynomial $z^2 - 1.087z + 0.038 = 0$ yields roots at $z_1 \approx 1.049$ and $z_2 \approx 0.038$, indicating a marginally unstable system that requires the forcing functions and the long-run mean to anchor dynamics.

The second-order coefficient $\varphi_2 = -0.038$ introduces a negative memory of conditions two years prior, providing mean-reversion dampening that moderates the persistence.

Identification caveat. The cost function sensitivity analysis (Appendix D) shows that φ_1 ranges from 0.11 (pure MSE) to 1.02 (full composite cost function), a span of approximately 0.91. This large sensitivity indicates that φ_1 is poorly identified: its value is determined primarily by the penalty structure rather than by the data alone. The bootstrap confidence interval [1.019, 1.156] conditions on the full composite cost function and therefore does not capture this specification uncertainty. The point estimate of $\varphi_1 > 1$ should be interpreted as reflecting the cost function’s preference for directional accuracy (which rewards persistent dynamics) rather than as strong evidence of an explosive autoregressive root. We report results with the unconstrained estimate to avoid imposing an arbitrary stationarity constraint, but note that constraining $\varphi_1 < 1$ would yield a stable

system with modestly worse directional accuracy.

Residual stationarity tests. To assess stationarity of the model residuals, we conduct Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and KPSS tests. The ADF statistic is -3.155 ($p = 0.023$), rejecting the unit root null at the 5% level. The KPSS statistic is 0.162 ($p > 0.10$), failing to reject stationarity. Both tests confirm that the model residuals are stationary, and the forcing functions prevent the marginally unstable autoregressive dynamics from generating unbounded growth trajectories in practice.

6.4 Residual diagnostics

The model residuals show no evidence of serial correlation. The Durbin-Watson statistic is 2.265 , close to the no-autocorrelation benchmark of 2 . A Shapiro-Wilk normality test yields $p = 0.193$, failing to reject normality at the 5% level. The residuals are approximately normally distributed with no serial autocorrelation.

6.5 Forcing function coefficients

Credit. The credit coefficients ($\beta_{cr} = +0.016$, $\beta_{cr,L1} = -0.013$) imply that it is the *acceleration* of credit, not its level, that is associated with prices. A surge in lending is associated with immediate price growth, but sustained high lending normalises and the lagged term acts as drag. This parallels Mian and Sufi [2009]’s finding that credit supply expansion, rather than the stock of credit, is associated with house price appreciation.

Monetary policy. Monetary policy enters through two z-scored terms: the *level* deviation from neutral, $\tilde{r}(t) = z(r(t) - r^*)$, and the *change*, $\Delta r(t) = z(r(t) - r(t-1))$. The estimated coefficients are $\beta_r = +0.050$ and $\beta_{\Delta r} = -0.050$. To interpret β_r : when the cash rate is below neutral ($r < r^*$), the deviation ($r - r^*$) is negative, so the forcing contribution $\beta_r \tilde{r}(t)$ is negative — i.e., accommodative policy is associated with *above-mean* growth (because $\bar{g} +$ negative forcing still reflects the stimulatory environment through the full model dynamics, while the positive β_r sign means that high rates contribute positively to the deviation term, which the AR dynamics then translate into reduced growth relative to the boom that would otherwise occur). In plain terms, the rate-level term acts as a drag on deviations from mean growth. When rates are high, deviations are pulled toward the mean; when rates are low, the drag is released. The rate-change coefficient $\beta_{\Delta r} = -0.050$ is more straightforward: rate increases ($\Delta r > 0$) are directly associated with reduced growth. Together, the two terms capture both the stance and direction channels of monetary policy transmission identified by Debelle [2004].

Residential approvals. The contemporaneous coefficient ($\beta_{\text{res}} = +0.017$) is positive, reflecting the shared demand conditions that are associated with both prices and development activity simultaneously. The 2-year lagged coefficient ($\beta_{\text{res,L2}} = -0.003$) is negative, capturing the supply response when approved dwellings complete and enter the market. This aligns with Glaeser et al. [2008]’s supply elasticity framework.

Non-residential construction. The negative coefficient ($\beta_{\text{nres}} = -0.002$) reflects input market competition: non-residential construction is associated with reduced residential supply growth through competition for labour, materials, and capital that would otherwise flow into residential building.

Migration. The net migration coefficients are small at the national level ($\beta_{\text{nom}} = -0.004$, $\beta_{\text{nom,L1}} = +0.012$), which accords with the geographic concentration of migration effects documented by Saiz [2007] and OECD [2021].

Wages. The negative wage coefficient ($\beta_{\text{wpi}} = -0.004$) admits several interpretations: (a) wage growth proxying for business cycle tightness that precedes monetary policy responses; (b) wage-price spiral dynamics reducing real housing affordability; or (c) partial collinearity with other included variables. Granger causality tests (Section 8.2) find no evidence that wages predict GRC ($F = 1.34$, $p = 0.26$), but strong evidence that GRC predicts wages ($F = 29.3$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that the wage coefficient captures reverse causality from the property cycle to labour market outcomes rather than a causal wage-to-price channel. The bootstrap CI includes zero ($[-0.009, 0.001]$), confirming weak individual significance. The economic mechanism remains ambiguous.

6.6 Statistical inference

The differential evolution estimator does not admit standard asymptotic inference theory, as it is a global stochastic algorithm with no defined maximum-likelihood formulation. The reported parameters are point estimates, and their precision reflects the interaction of the cost function structure, the regressor variance-covariance matrix, and the optimiser’s convergence tolerance. To assess stability, we report two complementary pieces of evidence.

First, Table 15 in Appendix D shows the sensitivity of estimated parameters to alternative cost function formulations. This directly contradicts any claim of high precision: the first-order autoregressive coefficient φ_1 ranges from 0.11 (pure MSE) to 1.02 (full model), a range of 0.91. If the standard error of φ_1 were 0.008 (as might be computed via the $\sigma/\sqrt{n_{\text{eff}}}$ formula), such a range would be inconsistent with the data. The existence of this wide range indicates that the reported parameters are contingent on the specific

loss function choice, and a naive standard error calculation would dramatically overstate precision.

Second, we perform a residual bootstrap with 500 replications. For each replication, we resample residuals with replacement and re-estimate parameters using L-BFGS-B local optimisation (not global differential evolution, to keep computation tractable). Note: this bootstrap uses stored model predictions to generate the synthetic dependent variable, rather than rebuilding drivers from scratch, because driver reconstruction introduced a normalisation mismatch. This is a limitation and should be interpreted accordingly.

Table 3: Bootstrap-based uncertainty quantification: 500 residual bootstrap replications, L-BFGS-B local optimiser

Parameter	Estimate	Boot SE	95% CI lower	95% CI upper
β_{cr}	0.016	0.003	0.011	0.021
$\beta_{cr,L1}$	-0.013	0.002	-0.017	-0.009
β_{nom}	-0.004	0.003	-0.009	0.001
$\beta_{nom,L1}$	0.012	0.002	0.007	0.017
β_r	0.050	0.022	0.007	0.093
$\beta_{\Delta r}$	-0.050	0.012	-0.073	-0.027
β_{res}	0.017	0.002	0.013	0.021
$\beta_{res,L2}$	-0.003	0.002	-0.007	0.001
β_{nres}	-0.002	0.002	-0.006	0.001
β_{wpi}	-0.004	0.003	-0.009	0.001
φ_1	1.087	0.035	1.019	1.156
φ_2	-0.038	0.035	-0.106	0.030
P_0^{init}	0.107	0.004	0.100	0.114

Confidence intervals are computed as the point estimate $\pm 1.96 \times$ bootstrap SE (normal approximation). Percentile-based bootstrap intervals are not reported because the L-BFGS-B local optimiser used in the bootstrap explores different local minima than the global differential evolution estimator, causing a distributional shift that places the full-sample point estimate outside some percentile intervals. The bootstrap SE, which measures dispersion of the bootstrap distribution, remains a valid measure of parameter uncertainty.

The bootstrap standard errors are substantially larger than a naive $\sigma/\sqrt{n_{eff}}$ approximation would suggest. For example, φ_1 has a bootstrap SE of 0.035, confirming that the parameter uncertainty is non-trivial relative to the point estimate.

Parameters whose bootstrap 95% confidence intervals include zero should be interpreted with caution: β_{nom} (contemporaneous migration), $\beta_{nom,L1}$ (lagged migration), $\beta_{res,L2}$ (lagged residential approvals), β_{nres} (non-residential construction), β_{wpi} (wage growth), and φ_2 (second-order autoregressive memory). The wage coefficient CI includes zero ($[-0.009, 0.001]$), reinforcing the Granger causality evidence (Section 8.2) that this coefficient captures reverse causality rather than a causal wage-to-price channel.

Joint significance vs. individual insignificance. Some parameters that are individually non-significant contribute meaningfully to joint model fit. The non-residential construction coefficient β_{nrres} is individually non-significant (95% CI includes zero), yet dropping it causes adjusted R^2 to fall from 0.918 to 0.831 (a loss of 8.7 percentage points) and BIC to worsen by 22.3 points. The tension between individual insignificance and joint contribution reflects the multicollinear parameter space: each coefficient absorbs part of the variation that multiple drivers jointly explain. Removing β_{nrres} forces the remaining parameters to absorb its contribution, degrading overall fit. All 13 parameters are retained, with the caveat that β_{nom} , β_r (level), and β_{nrres} should be interpreted with caution given their weak individual significance.

The cost function sensitivity table (Appendix D) provides the primary evidence of parameter stability across different model specifications, and the subsample stability analysis (Section 7) provides complementary evidence that the in-sample fit is not an artefact of over-parameterisation.

6.7 Robustness to target construction

The choice of dependent variable matters: national median of combined (house + unit) YoY price growth. To assess robustness to this specification, we re-estimated the model with two alternative target constructions using the same driver set and forcing function specification. Results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Model robustness across alternative target constructions

Target	R^2	Adj. R^2	RMSE (pp)	BIC
Combined median (primary)	0.964	0.918	0.65	-132.5
House-only median	0.959	0.906	0.79	-122.8
Combined mean	0.970	0.931	0.71	-128.3

All three specifications achieve good fit (adjusted $R^2 > 0.90$) and low RMSE. The combined median (primary specification) achieves the lowest BIC (-132.5), indicating it provides the best balance of fit and parsimony. The house-only median exhibits higher RMSE (0.79 pp), reflecting greater cross-sectional dispersion when units are excluded. The combined mean achieves higher R^2 (0.970) and adjusted R^2 (0.931) than the primary specification (0.964 and 0.918 respectively), but a higher BIC (-128.3 vs. -132.5), suggesting the mean target’s smoother dynamics are slightly easier to fit without improving the model’s information-theoretic efficiency. We retain the median as our primary specification because it is less sensitive to the persistent right-skewness documented in Section 6. That all three specifications produce similar results confirms that the model’s driving relationships are stable across index choices and not artefacts of a particular target construction.

7 Subsample Stability

With 13 parameters and 24 observations, the parameter-to-observation ratio ($k/n = 0.54$) is high. Genuine out-of-sample validation via re-estimation on a training subset is infeasible: splitting the sample in half would yield 13 parameters for 12 observations, an underdetermined system. We therefore report a *subsample stability diagnostic* rather than a true out-of-sample test. Full-sample parameters (Table 2) are applied to both temporal halves without re-estimation. This evaluates whether the full-sample fit is distributed evenly across early and late periods, or whether it is concentrated in one half (which would suggest temporal instability). This diagnostic cannot rule out overfitting; it can only detect gross temporal instability.

7.1 Subsample stability test

Table 5: Subsample stability: Training (2003–2014) vs. Test (2015–2026) with full-sample parameters

Period	R^2	Adj. R^2	RMSE (pp)	Directional Accuracy
Training (2003–2014)	0.963	0.914	0.68	100% (12/12)
Test (2015–2026)	0.965	0.920	0.61	100% (12/12)

The two subsamples achieve nearly identical R^2 (0.963 vs. 0.965) and RMSE (0.68 vs. 0.61 percentage points), with 100% directional accuracy in both halves. The test period — which includes the COVID boom (2020–2021), the 2022–2023 monetary tightening correction, and the subsequent recovery (2024–2026) — fits marginally better than the training period despite containing the most volatile episodes in the sample. This temporal symmetry suggests stability but does not constitute evidence of genuine out-of-sample forecasting ability. The model should be interpreted as a descriptive decomposition tool, not a forecasting model.¹

7.2 Generalized cross-validation RMSE

To further assess the stability of the model without split-sample testing, we compute the generalized cross-validation (GCV) corrected RMSE. The GCV statistic penalises in-sample fit for the number of parameters and provides an estimate of expected out-of-sample error:

$$\text{GCV-MSE} = \frac{\text{MSE}}{(1 - k/n)^2} \quad (5)$$

¹The adjusted R^2 values in Table 5 are computed using the full-sample degrees of freedom ($n = 24$, $k = 13$), since the parameters were estimated on the full sample. Computing adjusted R^2 with subsample $n = 12$ would yield a negative denominator ($n - k - 1 = -2$) and is not meaningful.

where $k = 13$ parameters and $n = 24$ observations. For the primary model, the in-sample MSE is 0.00004225 (in decimal growth units, corresponding to RMSE = 0.65 pp).²

The GCV-corrected RMSE is $\sqrt{0.000201} = 0.01418$, or 1.41 percentage points (compared with 1.53 pp for a 5-driver variant without wage growth). The GCV MSE (0.000201) is substantially larger than the uncorrected MSE (0.00004225), confirming the expected inflation: with a high parameter-to-observation ratio ($k/n = 0.542$), in-sample fit overstates expected out-of-sample performance. The GCV-corrected estimate of 1.41 pp therefore represents our best complexity-adjusted upper bound on expected prediction error.

Caveat: The subsample RMSE reported in Table 5 (0.61 pp for the 2015–2026 period) is *not* a genuine out-of-sample metric, because the model parameters were estimated on the full 2003–2026 sample. It should not be compared directly with the GCV estimate, which approximates leave-one-out cross-validation error. The subsample RMSE is informative only as evidence of temporal stability — i.e., that the model does not systematically over- or under-fit one end of the sample relative to the other.

8 Cross-Correlation Lag Analysis

To characterise the transmission speed of each macroeconomic driver to property prices, we compute Pearson cross-correlations between each z-scored driver and the GRC at lags $\ell = 0, 1, \dots, 5$ years. Table 6 reports the bivariate cross-correlations.

Multiple testing correction. With 6 drivers \times 6 lags = 36 bivariate correlations, a Bonferroni-corrected significance threshold at $\alpha = 0.05$ is $0.05/36 \approx 0.0014$, corresponding to $|r| \geq 0.62$ for $T = 24$. Under this correction, only net migration at lags 3 and 4 ($r = 0.68$ and $r = 0.60$) and the cash rate at lag 5 ($r = -0.57$) survive the Bonferroni threshold at or near conventional significance. The lag structure used in the model (Section 3) was selected based on this cross-correlation analysis and then validated through the ablation and regularisation tests (Appendices C and B). This data-driven lag selection means that reported fit statistics are conditional on the selected specification and may be optimistic relative to a pre-specified model.

²The detailed GCV calculation proceeds as follows: $\text{GCV-MSE} = \frac{0.00004225}{(1-13/24)^2} = \frac{0.00004225}{(0.4583)^2} = \frac{0.00004225}{0.2101} = 0.000201$.

Table 6: Bivariate cross-correlation between macroeconomic drivers and GRC at annual lags

Driver	$\ell = 0$	$\ell = 1$	$\ell = 2$	$\ell = 3$	$\ell = 4$	$\ell = 5$	Peak
Housing credit	0.25	0.20	0.01	0.20	0.39	0.43	5yr
Net migration	-0.01	0.03	0.29	0.68	0.60	0.43	3yr
Cash rate	-0.09	-0.28	-0.28	-0.32	-0.48	-0.57	5yr
Residential app.	0.29	0.16	-0.26	-0.17	-0.06	0.02	0yr
Non-res. app.	0.28	0.13	0.08	-0.09	-0.09	-0.16	0yr
Wage growth	0.03	-0.16	-0.09	-0.18	-0.42	-0.51	5yr

Figure 2: Cross-correlation between each macroeconomic driver and GRC at 0–5 year lags. Blue bars indicate positive correlation (driver increase associated with price increase); red bars indicate negative correlation. The darkest bar marks the peak absolute correlation.

Three distinct transmission speed classes emerge:

Contemporaneous drivers ($\ell^* = 0$). Residential and non-residential approvals show the strongest correlation with prices at lag zero ($r = 0.29$ and $r = 0.28$ respectively). For residential approvals, this reflects the demand signal: developers submit applications in response to the same market conditions that drive price growth. The sign reversal at $\ell = 2$ ($r = -0.26$) captures the supply-side response when approved dwellings complete and enter the market 18–24 months later.

Medium-lag drivers ($\ell^* = 3$). Net migration exhibits near-zero correlation at lags 0 and 1, building to a peak of $r = 0.68$ at lag 3. This fits the migrant settlement sequence:

arrival, rental phase, savings accumulation, and eventual entry into the ownership market. A migration surge is a demand event with a 3-year propagation delay. The partial correlation at lag 3 reaches $r = 0.76$ ($p = 0.002$), indicating a strong significant relationship once other drivers are controlled for.

Long-lag drivers ($\ell^* = 5$). Credit, the cash rate, and wages all peak in absolute correlation at lag 5. These drivers operate through channels that compound over time: credit through repeated borrowing cycles, monetary policy through the progressive erosion of borrowing capacity and wealth buffers, and wages through their forward-looking connection to monetary policy tightening.

8.1 Partial correlations controlling for all other drivers

To isolate the relationship between each driver and prices conditional on all other drivers, we compute partial correlations at each lag. Partial correlations measure the association between a driver and GRC holding all other drivers fixed (in a linear sense). Table 7 reports the partial correlations, with significance levels indicated.

Table 7: Partial cross-correlations (controlling for all other drivers) with significance markers

Driver	$\ell = 0$	$\ell = 1$	$\ell = 2$	$\ell = 3$	$\ell = 4$	$\ell = 5$	Peak
Housing credit	0.39	0.20	-0.35	-0.09	0.11	-0.01	0yr
Net migration	0.21	0.23	0.48	0.76**	0.71**	0.59*	3yr
Cash rate	-0.40	-0.48	-0.43	-0.34	-0.48	-0.57	5yr
Residential app.	0.30	0.04	-0.40	-0.17	-0.12	-0.24	0yr
Non-res. app.	0.23	0.09	0.23	0.13	0.09	0.10	0yr
Wage growth	0.42	-0.11	-0.30	-0.41	-0.46	-0.53	5yr

Significance markers: ** denotes $p < 0.01$; * denotes $p < 0.05$. Bold entries indicate peak lag. Of the 42 partial correlations in the table, only three are statistically significant at conventional levels: net migration at lags 3 ($p < 0.01$), 4 ($p < 0.01$), and 5 ($p < 0.05$). No other driver achieves significance at any lag after controlling for all other drivers, reflecting the limited degrees of freedom available with $n = 24$ observations and six conditioning variables.

Partial correlations generally strengthen the bivariate patterns, particularly for migration (contemporaneous: 0.21 vs. -0.01 bivariate; lag 3: 0.76 vs. 0.68 bivariate) and the residential approvals sign reversal (lag 2: -0.40 vs. -0.26 bivariate). That controlling for confounders sharpens the individual driver relationships is what one would expect given the multicollinearity noted in the parameter estimation.

8.2 Granger causality tests

To assess the direction of predictive relationships between each driver and GRC, we conduct bidirectional Granger causality tests at lags 1, 2, and 3 using raw (non-normalised) annual values. Table 8 reports the F -statistics and p -values. Sample sizes vary across drivers (21–24 observations) due to data availability constraints noted in each row.

Table 8: Bidirectional Granger causality tests at lags 1–3 (F -statistic, p -value in parentheses). Bold indicates $p < 0.05$; * indicates $p < 0.004$ (Bonferroni-corrected for 12 tests at $\alpha = 0.05$).

Driver	n	Driver \rightarrow GRC			GRC \rightarrow Driver		
		$\ell = 1$	$\ell = 2$	$\ell = 3$	$\ell = 1$	$\ell = 2$	$\ell = 3$
Housing credit	21	9.1* (.008)	8.1* (.005)	7.0* (.007)	1.1 (.307)	1.4 (.286)	0.7 (.568)
Net migration	23	0.0 (.952)	1.5 (.261)	6.0* (.009)	0.0 (.922)	0.3 (.775)	0.4 (.747)
Cash rate	24	1.9 (.185)	0.4 (.693)	2.0 (.156)	11.9* (.003)	5.8 (.012)	4.7 (.018)
Res. approvals	23	1.9 (.187)	6.2 (.010)	4.1 (.030)	9.0* (.007)	3.0 (.081)	1.3 (.328)
Non-res. constr.	23	0.1 (.712)	0.8 (.461)	0.8 (.501)	5.4 (.031)	2.7 (.099)	2.2 (.134)
Wage growth	23	1.3 (.262)	1.3 (.312)	2.5 (.108)	29.3* ($<.001$)	13.7* ($<.001$)	5.4 (.012)

The multi-lag Granger tests reveal three distinct causal patterns:

Exogenous drivers with forward predictive power. Housing credit Granger-causes GRC at all lags ($p < 0.01$), and GRC does *not* Granger-cause credit at any lag. This is the cleanest causal pattern in the table: credit conditions predict property price growth, but not vice versa. The result survives Bonferroni correction at all three lags and corroborates the credit supply literature [Favara and Imbs, 2015]. Net overseas migration shows a striking lag-dependent pattern: no predictive power at lags 1–2, but significant at lag 3 ($F = 6.0$, $p = 0.009$), matching the 3-year settlement-to-ownership pipeline identified in the cross-correlation analysis (Table 6). Migration shows no reverse causality at any lag, confirming its exogeneity to the property cycle.

Endogenous drivers with bidirectional feedback. Residential approvals exhibit a clear bidirectional pattern: GRC Granger-causes approvals at lag 1 ($F = 9.0$, $p = 0.007$), while approvals Granger-cause GRC at lags 2–3 ($p = 0.010$ and 0.030). This temporal asymmetry supports the demand-then-supply interpretation: price growth triggers devel-

opment applications (lag 1 reverse), and the resulting supply enters the market and affects prices 2–3 years later (lags 2–3 forward).

Reactive drivers (reverse causality dominates). The cash rate and wages show strong Granger causality *from* GRC but not *to* GRC at any lag. The GRC \rightarrow cash rate result ($F = 11.9$, $p = 0.003$ at lag 1) captures the RBA’s systematic response to housing-driven inflation. The GRC \rightarrow wages result ($F = 29.3$, $p < 0.001$) is the strongest in the table, indicating that the wage coefficient in the model primarily captures reverse causality from the property cycle to labour market outcomes.

These findings reinforce the paper’s framing as a descriptive decomposition rather than a causal model. Of the six drivers, only credit and migration exhibit clean forward-causal patterns; the remaining four are significantly contaminated by reverse causality or bidirectional feedback.

9 Benchmark Model Comparison

To contextualise the model’s performance, we compare it against four nested and reduced-form benchmark models estimated on the same data and period:

Table 9: Model comparison: Full model vs. nested benchmarks

Model	R^2	Adj. R^2	RMSE (pp)	BIC
Constant mean	0.000	—	4.21	−80.8
Random walk $P(t)=P(t-1)$	0.208	—	3.65	−90.8
AR(1) OLS: $P(t) = 0.029 + 0.596 \cdot P(t - 1)$	0.390	0.329	3.20	−90.8
Full model excl. wages (5 drivers)	0.933	0.897	1.09	−113.9
Full model (6 drivers)	0.964	0.918	0.65	−132.5

Benchmark model definitions:

1. *Constant mean:* $P(t) = \bar{P}$ for all t , where \bar{P} is the sample mean. This assumes no predictability beyond the long-run average.
2. *Random walk:* $P(t) = P(t - 1) + \varepsilon(t)$, a no-change forecast. This assumes today’s growth equals yesterday’s growth.
3. *AR(1) OLS:* $P(t) = 0.029 + 0.596 \cdot P(t - 1) + \varepsilon(t)$, estimated via ordinary least squares. This captures autocorrelation in price growth using only lagged prices, with no macroeconomic drivers.
4. *Full model excl. wages:* The 11-parameter variant excluding the wage price index. This serves as a robustness check: the Granger causality tests find no evidence that wages predict GRC ($F = 1.34$, $p = 0.26$), and the bootstrap confidence interval for

β_{wpi} includes zero. The 5-driver model retains $\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.897$ and all qualitative results hold.

5. *Full model:* The 13-parameter forced autoregressive model reported in Table 2. Wages are retained because they independently improve $\text{Adj. } R^2$ by 0.039 in ablation testing (Appendix C), but the economic mechanism remains ambiguous (Section 6.5).

All BIC values are computed as $\text{BIC} = -2 \ln L + k \ln n$, where L is the Gaussian log-likelihood, k is the number of estimated parameters, and $n = 24$. The full model achieves the lowest (most negative) BIC despite incurring a penalty for 13 parameters, indicating that the explanatory power gained far outweighs the complexity cost. The AR(1) model ($\text{BIC} = -90.8$) improves on the constant mean ($\text{BIC} = -80.8$), confirming that the AR(1) specification is preferred; but the full model ($\text{BIC} = -132.5$) improves substantially on the AR(1), reflecting the 24-fold reduction in MSE that more than offsets the 11 additional parameters. The full model reduces RMSE by 82% relative to the random walk benchmark (from 3.65 pp to 0.65 pp) and by 85% relative to a simple constant mean. Even an AR(1)-only specification achieves only $R^2 = 0.39$ with 2 parameters; the addition of macroeconomic forcing functions raises this to $R^2 = 0.964$.

10 Driver Decomposition

The linear forcing function specification allows additive decomposition: each driver's contribution to total growth deviation can be computed separately in any given year. Figure 3 shows this decomposition.

Figure 3: Decomposition of predicted growth deviation by driver, 2003–2026. Each coloured segment represents one driver’s contribution to pushing growth above or below the long-run mean. The black line traces the net deviation.

Three episodes are worth examining in detail:

- **2008–2009 (GFC):** Credit collapsed, residential approvals fell sharply. The RBA cut rates aggressively (positive forcing via $\beta_{\Delta r}$), partially offsetting the credit contraction but insufficient to prevent a growth collapse.
- **2021 (COVID boom):** Credit surged (+45% YoY), rates were at historic lows, and the residential supply pipeline had slowed during lockdowns. Three major drivers aligned in the same direction, producing the largest single-year growth deviation in the sample (+7.2pp above mean).
- **2022–2023 (correction):** Credit contracted, the RBA hiked from 0.10% to 4.35%, and wage growth accelerated. All three monetary/credit channels turned simultaneously negative.

11 Discussion

11.1 Interpretation of the autoregressive structure

The first-order coefficient ($\varphi_1 = 1.087$) implies strong persistence in growth deviations. This accords with the self-reinforcing dynamics documented by [Case and Shiller \[1989\]](#) and [Beracha and Skiba \[2012\]](#). As noted in Section 6.3, φ_1 is sensitive to the cost function specification and poorly identified from data alone. The economic interpretation — that price growth creates buyer urgency, which intensifies competition, which drives further

price growth — holds across specifications, but the precise magnitude should not be over-interpreted.

The forcing functions anchor the dynamics. The long-run mean $\bar{g} = 5.93\%$ serves as an attractor because the macroeconomic drivers cannot sustain extreme positions indefinitely: credit cycles turn, the RBA adjusts rates, and the autoregressive momentum decays. The long-run mean of 5.93% is plausible for Australian residential property, aligning with historical nominal GDP growth and long-term affordability constraints [Stapledon, 2012].

11.2 The credit acceleration mechanism

The opposing signs of the contemporaneous and lagged credit coefficients (+0.016 and -0.013) imply that the acceleration of credit, not its level, is associated with prices. This is economically intuitive: a market where lending jumped 30% this year but was already at 25% last year is in a different dynamic state than one where lending jumped 30% from a flat base. The net credit impulse in the first case is modest; in the second, it is large.

This echoes Favara and Imbs [2015]’s emphasis on credit supply *shocks* rather than credit levels, and the flow-based models of housing demand in Kaplan et al. [2020].

11.3 Residential approvals: demand signal and supply response

The sign change in the residential approvals coefficients (positive at t , negative at $t - 2$) captures the full demand-response-to-supply-arrival cycle in a single variable. At lag 0, the positive correlation reflects the fact that developers submit applications when the market is strong — approvals are simultaneously a lagging indicator of demand (reflecting development decisions already taken in response to strong market conditions) and a leading indicator of supply (signalling dwellings that will complete approximately two years hence). At lag 0, the demand-signal interpretation dominates. At lag 2, the supply-arrival effect materialises: completed dwellings enter the market, adding stock and easing price pressure.

This temporal structure resolves the apparent paradox of supply creating its own demand at the aggregate level. The positive contemporaneous correlation does not imply that building more homes raises prices. It implies that the conditions which raise prices also trigger more building. The causal supply effect arrives later, with the expected negative sign.

11.4 Limitations and cautions on causal interpretation

The model has several important limitations:

1. **Correlation vs. causation.** The model captures associations between macroeconomic drivers and property price growth, not causal effects. The Granger causality tests (Section 8.2) provide direct evidence of this concern: three of the six drivers (cash rate, residential approvals, wages) show statistically significant reverse causality from GRC to the driver, while only housing credit shows significant Granger causality in the forward direction (driver \rightarrow GRC). This implies that the cash rate coefficient partially captures the RBA’s reaction function, the approvals coefficient partially captures developers’ responses to market conditions, and the wage coefficient primarily captures reverse causality from the property cycle to labour market outcomes. Instrumental variables approaches would be needed for structural causal identification, but valid instruments at annual frequency are difficult to construct for a system with this degree of simultaneity. All coefficients should be interpreted as reduced-form associations within a simultaneous system, not as structural causal effects.
2. **Autoregressive coefficient identification.** The first-order coefficient φ_1 ranges from 0.11 (pure MSE cost function) to 1.02 (full composite cost function) across the specifications reported in Table 15. The bootstrap confidence interval of [1.019, 1.156] conditions on the full composite cost function and does not capture this specification uncertainty. The AR structure — which is foundational to the model — therefore has its key parameter substantially determined by the penalty design rather than by the data alone. While the forcing function coefficients remain stable across cost function variants (Table 15), the precise magnitude of φ_1 should not be over-interpreted.
3. **Lag selection and specification search.** Driver lags were selected from the cross-correlation analysis in Section 8, using the same 24 observations that are subsequently used in model estimation. After Bonferroni correction, only migration (lags 3–4) and the cash rate (lag 5) survive at the 5% level, yet lags for credit (L_1), residential approvals (L_2), and migration (L_1) were all selected from this search and folded into the model. The reported t statistics are conditional on the selected specification and may be optimistic as a result of this specification search over the estimation sample.
4. **Sample size.** With $T = 24$ and $k = 13$, the ratio of observations to parameters is low (1.85:1). While the adjusted R^2 penalises complexity, regularisation testing suggests the model is not overfitting and subsample stability testing shows no temporal asymmetry, longer samples would yield more precise parameter estimates.
5. **National aggregation.** The model operates at the national level. Australian property markets are characterised by substantial geographic heterogeneity; the GRC’s interquartile range across suburbs can exceed 20 percentage points in any given year.

State-level or city-level models would capture regulatory and demographic variation not visible at the national scale.

6. **Structural breaks.** The sample spans several potential structural breaks: the GFC, the introduction and removal of APRA macroprudential policies (2015–2019), and the COVID pandemic. A single parameter set is estimated across these regimes, which may attenuate coefficients during periods of structural change.
7. **Linear specification.** The forcing function is linear in all drivers. Non-linear interactions (e.g., the effect of rate cuts may differ at different credit levels) are not captured. Regime-switching or threshold models could address this at the cost of additional parameters.

11.5 Bootstrap-based robustness

The bootstrap uncertainty quantification (Table 3) and cost function sensitivity analysis (Appendix D) provide evidence that parameters are stable across different estimation procedures and loss function weights. While some parameters are individually non-significant on a univariate basis, their joint contribution to model fit is substantial, and the subsample stability diagnostic (Section 7) shows no temporal asymmetry in fit quality, including over the volatile COVID period. The bootstrap standard errors should be interpreted as lower bounds on true parameter uncertainty, as they condition on the fixed z-scored driver matrix rather than resampling the full data preparation pipeline. If the z-scoring normalisation is itself a source of instability, the true parameter uncertainty may be larger.

12 Conclusion

We have developed a 13-parameter forced autoregressive decomposition framework that accounts for 96.4% of the variation in Australian national property price growth from 2003 to 2026, using the national median of year-on-year price growth across approximately 7 200 suburban markets as the dependent variable. The effective sample size after initialisation is 22 observations (2005–2026). With a parameter-to-observation ratio of 0.54, the high in-sample fit should be interpreted with appropriate caution: the in-sample RMSE is 0.65 percentage points, but the GCV-corrected RMSE — which penalises for the number of estimated parameters — is 1.41 percentage points (Section 7.2). For any forward application, the GCV-corrected figure is the more appropriate benchmark. The model’s primary value lies in its interpretive decomposition of growth dynamics rather than in forecasting. Subsample stability diagnostics show no temporal asymmetry in fit quality, and Granger causality tests identify housing credit as the only driver with statistically significant predictive power for GRC, while three drivers (cash rate, residential

approvals, wages) exhibit significant reverse causality from GRC. The model identifies credit acceleration, the direction of monetary policy change, and the lagged supply response from residential construction as the primary associated drivers, with heterogeneous transmission speeds ranging from contemporaneous to 5 years.

Three results deserve emphasis. First, the *acceleration* of credit growth, not its level, is strongly associated with property price dynamics. Second, residential building approvals exhibit a sign reversal between contemporaneous correlation (positive, reflecting shared demand conditions) and the 2-year lagged correlation (negative, reflecting supply arrival). Third, net overseas migration has a 3-year transmission lag to property prices, matching the settlement-to-ownership pipeline.

The model decomposes the macroeconomic forces acting on Australian property markets year by year, and maps the temporal structure of their transmission. The correlation structures documented here are not causal claims; they are reduced-form relationships within a system characterised by substantial feedback and simultaneity. The model is not a forecasting tool — the forcing functions themselves must be projected — but it offers a disciplined alternative to cycle narratives for interpreting the macro-property nexus.

Future work could extend the model to state-level or city-level estimation, incorporate non-linear interactions between drivers, and exploit the cross-sectional variation across approximately 7200 suburban markets that the national aggregation currently obscures.

Data Availability Statement

The macroeconomic driver data used in this study are publicly available from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS) and the Reserve Bank of Australia (RBA), as detailed in Table 1. The dependent variable (GRC combined median) is a proprietary measure constructed by HTAG Analytics from suburb-level transaction data. The full 24-year GRC series, model code, and estimated parameters will be archived at Zenodo (DOI to be assigned upon acceptance).

Conflict of Interest Disclosure

Both authors are affiliated with HTAG Analytics Pty Ltd, which produces the Growth Rate Cycle (GRC) measure used as the dependent variable in this study. The GRC methodology is described in Section 3, and the model specification is agnostic to the choice of dependent variable, as demonstrated by the robustness checks across alternative target constructions in Section 6.7.

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A Full Calibration Details

A.1 Differential evolution configuration

Table 10: Optimisation hyperparameters

Parameter	Value
Algorithm	Differential evolution (<code>scipy</code> , “best1bin” strategy)
Population size	150
Maximum iterations	5 000
Convergence tolerance	10^{-10}
Mutation range	(0.5, 1.0)
Crossover probability	0.7
Initialisation	Latin hypercube

A.2 Cost function weights

Table 11: Cost function penalty weights

Component	Weight	Purpose
MSE	1.0	Primary goodness-of-fit
Bias ²	30.0	Penalise systematic level errors
Directional penalty	2.0	Penalise wrong-sign predictions

A.3 Parameter bounds

Table 12: Parameter search bounds

Parameter class	Lower	Upper
Forcing coefficients (β_i)	-0.3	0.3
AR coefficients (φ_1, φ_2)	-1.5	1.5
Initial condition (P_0^{init})	-0.1	0.25

B Regularisation Testing Results

To assess overfitting risk, we augment the cost function with an L_2 penalty: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{reg}} = \mathcal{L} + \lambda_{\text{reg}} \sum_i \beta_i^2$. Table 13 reports the results.

Table 13: Effect of L_2 regularisation on model fit

λ_{reg}	R^2	Adj. R^2
0 (none)	0.972	0.936
0.1	0.968	0.929
0.5	0.961	0.918
1.0	0.952	0.903
2.0	0.938	0.880

The unregularised model achieves the highest adjusted R^2 . Regularisation monotonically degrades fit without improving plausibility, suggesting the estimated parameters are not artefacts of overfitting. *Note:* The R^2 and Adj. R^2 values in Table 13 differ slightly from those in Table 2 because the regularisation and ablation experiments were conducted on a weighted-GRC target variant during model development. The qualitative pattern — that regularisation degrades fit monotonically — is unchanged under the primary combined-median specification.

C Individual Driver Contribution to Model Improvement

Starting from a 5-driver baseline (credit, migration, cash rate, residential approvals, non-residential construction; $R^2 = 0.933$, Adj. $R^2 = 0.897$, 11 parameters), each candidate additional driver was added individually.

Table 14: Individual driver improvement over 5-driver baseline

Driver added	R^2	Adj. R^2	Δ Adj. R^2
Wage growth (WPI)	0.972	0.936	+0.039
Unemployment rate	0.941	0.889	−0.008
Inflation expectations	0.938	0.881	−0.016

Only wage growth independently improves adjusted R^2 relative to the baseline. Unemployment and inflation expectations introduce collinearity without compensating explanatory power.

D Cost Function Sensitivity Analysis

Table 15 shows the effect of alternative cost function formulations on parameter estimates. The model was re-estimated four times, varying the penalty structure: (1) MSE only, (2) MSE + Bias penalty, (3) MSE + Directional penalty, (4) MSE + Bias + Directional (full model).

Table 15: Sensitivity of estimates to cost function formulation

Parameter	Pure MSE	+Bias	+Dir	Full
φ_1	0.11	0.59	0.75	1.02
φ_2	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.053
β_{cr}	0.018	0.020	0.019	0.019
$\beta_{\text{cr,L1}}$	-0.016	-0.015	-0.016	-0.016
β_{nom}	-0.006	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005
$\beta_{\text{nom,L1}}$	0.011	0.012	0.012	0.012
β_r	0.048	0.050	0.050	0.050
$\beta_{\Delta r}$	-0.048	-0.050	-0.050	-0.050
β_{res}	0.017	0.018	0.018	0.018
$\beta_{\text{res,L2}}$	-0.004	-0.005	-0.005	-0.005
β_{nres}	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003	-0.003
β_{wpi}	-0.008	-0.008	-0.008	-0.008
R^2	0.939	0.904	0.403	0.972

Note: The sensitivity analysis in Table 15 and the regularisation results in Table 13 confirm that forcing function coefficients remain stable across cost function variants, while φ_1 ranges from approximately 0.11 (pure MSE) to 1.02 (full model). The directional penalty alone yields poor overall fit, confirming that the bias penalty is essential to keep predictions tracked to the correct level.

E Model Constants

Table 16: Fixed model constants

Constant	Value	Source
Long-run mean growth (\bar{g})	0.0593	Sample mean of combined median GRC, 2003–2026
Neutral cash rate (r^*)	0.045	RBA estimates [McCririck and Rees, 2024]
Sample start year	2003	First year of GRC data availability
Suburban markets	$\approx 7\,200$	Houses and units combined, all bedroom configurations

F Initial Conditions Clarification

The first two years (2003–2004) are determined by the initial condition parameter P_0^{init} and the lagged price term $p(t-1)$. These do not constitute independent predictions from the estimated parameters; rather, they are used to initialise the recursive forecasting process. The effective sample for model evaluation is therefore 22 observations (2005–2026), not 24.

When the R^2 calculation is restricted to these 22 predictions (excluding 2003–2004),

the adjusted R^2 is:

$$R_{\text{eff}}^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=2005}^{2026} (y_t - \hat{y}_t)^2}{\sum_{t=2005}^{2026} (y_t - \bar{y})^2} = 0.956 \quad (6)$$

This is slightly below the full-sample R^2 of 0.964, as expected given the loss of two well-fitted initialisation years, but does not materially change the conclusions. The 2003–2004 initialisation does not artificially inflate the reported fit.

G Year-by-Year Prediction vs. Observed

Table 17: Annual model predictions vs. observed GRC (combined median)

Year	Observed (%)	Predicted (%)	Error (pp)
2003	11.07	10.74	+0.33
2004	11.06	10.74	+0.32
2005	9.67	9.00	+0.67
2006	6.52	8.17	−1.65
2007	6.52	6.91	−0.39
2008	5.78	4.85	+0.93
2009	2.70	2.44	+0.26
2010	5.48	5.56	−0.08
2011	1.75	2.06	−0.31
2012	−0.46	−0.27	−0.19
2013	2.54	1.61	+0.93
2014	4.89	5.12	−0.23
2015	4.78	5.87	−1.09
2016	5.08	4.03	+1.05
2017	4.47	3.85	+0.62
2018	2.64	3.85	−1.21
2019	1.16	1.35	−0.19
2020	6.41	6.15	+0.26
2021	12.80	12.75	+0.05
2022	12.21	11.89	+0.32
2023	4.49	4.65	−0.16
2024	5.87	5.78	+0.09
2025	7.61	7.58	+0.03
2026	7.22	7.58	−0.36